

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

EXPANSION OF THE GREEN FUNCTION OF INTEGRO-DIFFERENTIAL OPERATOR L_θ

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Abstract

For obtaining formulas of expansions of the integro-differential operator L_θ in eigen-functions, at first we consider a boundary value problem in the finite interval $[a; b], b > 0$, write formulas of expansions in eigen-functions and then tending $b \rightarrow \infty$ we obtain expansion for the integro-differential operator L_θ .

To obtain expansion of the Green function $T_\theta(x, \tau, \lambda)$ of the integro-differential operator L_θ we will assume that

- 1) the conditions $|\rho(x)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(x, s, \rho)| ds \right] < ce^{-2\varepsilon_0 x}, \varepsilon_0 > 0$ are fulfilled.
- 2) $F_i(\rho) = y'_i(0, \rho) - \theta y_1(0, \rho)$ does not vanish at the points of the real axis $\rho_1; \rho = \rho_1 + i\rho_2, \rho_1 = \text{Re } \rho$.
- 3) the zeros $F_i(\rho)$ are simple.

Keywords: integro-differential, Green function, kernel, operator, eigen-values, set, condition, finite, number, theorem, proof, solution, equation, series, asymptotics, integral, estimation.

Introduction.

Denote by L_θ an operator generated by the integro-differential expression

$$l(y) \equiv -y''(x) + p(x)y'(x) + \int_0^\infty k(x, s, \rho)y'(s, \rho)ds \quad (3.1)$$

and the boundary condition

$$y'(0) - \theta y(0) = 0 \quad (3.2)$$

in the Hilbert space $L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$, $\mathbb{R}^+ = (0, \infty)$, where θ is a fixed complex number.

The domain of definition $D(L_\theta)$ of the integro-differential operator L_θ consists of the functions $y(x)$ having the derivative $y'(x)$ absolutely continuous in each finite interval $(0, b) \subset \mathbb{R}^+$, satisfying the boundary condition (3.2) and such that $y(x) \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$ and $l(y) \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$. If $y(x) \in D(L_\theta)$, then by the definition $L_\theta y = l(y)$.

Let us consider in $L^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$ the integro-differential equation

$$l(y) = \lambda y \quad (3.3)$$

and rewrite it in the form

$$y''(x) + \lambda y(x) = p(x)y'(x) + \int_0^\infty k(x, s, \rho)y'(s)ds. \quad (3.4)$$

Let $\rho(x)$ be a complex-valued summable function in the interval $\mathbb{R}^+$ and the kernel of the integro-differential equation (3.4) is of the form:

$$k(x, s, \rho) = \begin{cases} e^{-\rho\omega_1(s-x)} \rho(s) k^*(x, s, \rho) & \text{for } s < x, \\ e^{-\rho\omega_2(s-x)} \rho(s) k^*(x, s, \rho) & \text{for } s > x, \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

where ω_1, ω_2 are second degree roots from -1, while $k^*(x, s, \rho)$ is a complex-valued continuous bounded function on totality of variables (x, s, ρ) , $0 \leq x, s < \infty$, $\text{Im}\rho > 0$ and analytic with respect to ρ in the domain $\text{Im}\rho > 0$ for each fixed (x, s) , $0 \leq x, s < \infty$, $\sqrt{\lambda} = \rho = \rho_1 + i\rho_2$, $\rho_1 = \text{Re}\rho$, $\rho_2 = \text{Im}\rho$.

In this paper, everywhere we will assume that the following auxiliary constraint is fulfilled: there exist such $\varepsilon > 0$ that

$$1) \quad |\rho(x)| \left[1 + \int_0^\infty |k^*(x, s, \rho)| ds \right] < ce^{-2\varepsilon x}, \quad \varepsilon > 0. \quad (3.6)$$

2) $F_1(\rho) = y_1'(0, \rho) - \theta y_1(0, \rho)$ does not vanish at the points of the real axis $\rho_1 = \text{Re}\rho$.

3) the zeros $F_1(\rho)$ are simple.

If condition (3.6) is fulfilled then by lemma 1.5 (see V), $E_1(\rho)$ is analytic in the half-plane

$$\rho_2 = \text{Im}\rho > -\frac{\varepsilon_0}{2}.$$

Since $F_1(\rho)$ does not vanish for rather large ρ , then the number of zeros $F_1(\rho)$ can be only finite.

Let $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n$ be all eigen-values of the integro-differential operator L_θ , while $y_1(x), y_2(x), \dots, y_n(x)$ are the eigen-function corresponding to them.

We now choose $C_{R,\delta}$ on the complex ρ - plane of the form:

$C_{R,\delta}$ consists of the straight line $\rho_2 = \delta > 0$ from $\rho_1 = -\sqrt{R^2 - \delta^2}$ to $\rho_1 = \sqrt{R^2 - \delta^2}$ and the arch of the circle $\rho = \text{Re}^{i\theta}$ from $\theta = \gamma = \arcsin \frac{\delta}{R}$ to $\theta = \pi - \gamma = \pi - \arcsin \frac{\delta}{R}$.

Choose δ and R so that $\sqrt{\lambda}$ lies inside the contour $C_{R,\delta}$.

Let us consider the integral

$$J_{R,\delta} = \int_{C_{R,\delta}} \frac{T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho)}{\rho^2 - \lambda} \rho d\rho, \quad \text{where } R \geq R_0.$$

If λ_0 is an eigen-value of the integro-differential operator L_θ , then $\text{Im}\sqrt{\lambda_0} \neq \delta$; $\sqrt{\lambda_0}$ and $R_0^2 > |\lambda_0|$ from

$$T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho) = M(x, \tau, \rho) + \int_0^\infty \Gamma(x, t, \rho) \cdot M(t, \tau, \rho) dt.$$

It is clear that

$$T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho) = \begin{cases} \frac{y_1(x, \rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} \left[\frac{F_2(\rho)}{F_1(\rho)} y_1(\tau, \rho) - y_2(\tau, \rho) \right] + \int_0^\infty \frac{\Gamma(x, t, \rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} \times \\ \times \left[\frac{F_2(\rho)}{F_1(\rho)} y_1(\tau, \rho) - y_2(\tau, \rho) \right] y_1(t, \rho) dt \text{ for } \tau < x, \\ \frac{y_1(\tau, \rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} \left[\frac{F_2(\rho)}{F_1(\rho)} y_1(x, \rho) - y_2(x, \rho) \right] + \int_0^\infty \frac{\Gamma(x, t, \rho)}{2\rho\omega_1} \times \\ \times \left[\frac{F_2(\rho)}{F_1(\rho)} y_1(t, \rho) - y_2(t, \rho) \right] y_1(\tau, \rho) dt \text{ for } \tau > x. \end{cases} \tag{3.7}$$

Since $T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho)$ is the ratio of two functions, each of which is analytic for $\rho_2 = Jm\rho > 0$, then the singularities at the points $\rho^2 = \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_n$ will be poles.

Then we can write the expansion $T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho)$ in the vicinity of the point λ_i :

$$T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i(x) \overline{y_i(\tau)}}{(\lambda - \lambda_i) [y_i, y_i]} - \frac{\omega_1}{2\pi} J_{R, \delta}$$

where $(y_i, y_i) = \int_0^\infty y_i(\tau) \overline{y_i(\tau)} d\tau$.

The residues with respect to the remaining points $\rho^2 = \lambda_i$ of the Green function will be

$$-\frac{1}{2} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i(x) \overline{y_i(\tau)}}{(\lambda_i - \lambda) (y_i, y_i)}$$

In what follows, we calculate $J_{R, \delta}$

$$J_{R, \delta} = \int_\gamma^{\pi-\gamma} T_\theta(x, \tau, \text{Re}^{\omega_1\theta}) \omega_1 R^2 e^{2\omega_1\theta} \cdot d\theta + \int_{-\sqrt{R^2-\delta^2}}^{\sqrt{R^2-\delta^2}} \frac{(\rho_1 + \omega_1\delta) T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho_1 + \omega_1\delta)}{(\rho_1 + \omega_1\delta)^2 - \lambda} d\rho_1.$$

It obvious that

$$\begin{aligned} |T_\theta(x, \tau, \text{Re}^{\omega_1\theta})| &= \left| \frac{y_1(x) \overline{y_1(\tau)}}{R^2 e^{2\omega_1\theta} - \lambda_1} + \frac{y_2(x) \overline{y_2(\tau)}}{R^2 e^{2\omega_1\theta} - \lambda_2} + \dots + \frac{y_n(x) \overline{y_n(\tau)}}{R^2 e^{2\omega_1\theta} - \lambda_n} \right| \leq \\ &\leq \frac{y_1(x) \overline{y_1(\tau)}}{R^2} + \frac{1}{R^2}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i(x) \overline{y_i(\tau)}}{R^2} \leq 1$ for fixed x, τ beginning from rather large R .

Therefore

$$\left| \int_\gamma^{\pi-\gamma} \frac{T_\theta(x, \tau, R^2 e^{2\omega_1\theta})}{R^2 e^{2\omega_1\theta} - \lambda} d\theta \right| \leq \frac{y_1(x) \overline{y_1(\tau)}}{R^2}, \text{ i.e.}$$

for fixed x, τ we have:

$$\lim_{R \rightarrow \infty} \int_\gamma^{\pi-\gamma} \frac{T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho, \text{Re}^{2\omega_1\theta}) \omega_1 R^2 e^{2\omega_1\theta}}{R^2 e^{2\omega_1\theta} - \lambda} d\theta = 0.$$

In the similar way we can prove that

$$\left| \frac{(\rho_1 + \omega_1 \delta) T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho_1 + \omega_1 \delta)}{(\rho_1 + \omega_1 \delta)^2 - \lambda} \right| \leq \frac{c}{\rho_1^2}$$

for rather large R .

It follows from the obtained estimations that

$$\lim_{R \rightarrow \infty} J_{R, \delta} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(\rho_1 + \omega_1 \delta) T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho_1 + \omega_1 \delta)}{(\rho_1 + \omega_1 \delta)^2 - \lambda} d\rho_1$$

exists and the integral from the right converge absolutely and uniformly with respect to x, τ for $Im\rho \geq \delta_1 > \delta > 0$.

Then

$$T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i(x) \overline{y_i(\tau)}}{(\lambda_i - \lambda)(y_i, y_i)} - \frac{\omega_1}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{(\rho_1 + \omega_1 \delta) T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho_1 + \omega_1 \delta)}{(\rho_1 + \omega_1 \delta)^2 - \lambda} d\rho_1.$$

So, we obtain

Theorem 3.1. For $\delta > 0$ for the Green function $T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho)$ we have the representation (3.8). In what follows, we will assume the following:

$$1) \int_0^{\infty} e^{2\varepsilon_0 x} |\rho(x)| \left[1 + \int_0^{\infty} |k^*(s, x, \rho)| ds \right] dx < B_1 < \infty \quad (3.9)$$

where $\varepsilon_0 > \varepsilon > 0$, and β_1 does not depend on ρ .

2) $F_1(\rho) = y_1'(0, \rho) - \theta y_1(0, \rho)$ does not vanish at the points of the real axis ρ_1 ,

3) The zeros $F_i(\rho)$ are simple.

If condition (3.9) is fulfilled, then $F_i(\rho)$ is analytic in the half-plane $Im\rho > -\varepsilon_0/2$. Since $F_i(\rho)$ does not vanish for rather large ρ then the number of zeros $F_i(\rho)$ can be only a finitely many.

Since λ is not an eigen-value and $F_i(\rho)$ does not vanish at the points of the real axis ρ_1 then the integral (3.8) converges as $\delta \rightarrow 0$ as well, i.e.

$$T_\theta(x, \tau, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i(x) \overline{y_i(\tau)}}{(\lambda_i - \lambda)(y_i, y_i)} - \frac{\omega_1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\rho_1 T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho_1) - \rho_1 T_\theta(x, \tau, -\rho_1)}{\rho_1^2 - \lambda} d\rho_1. \quad (3.10)$$

Now let us transform the expression

$$\rho_1 T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho_1) - \rho_1 T_\theta(x, \tau, -\rho_1).$$

Using (3.7) for $\tau < x$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_1 T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho_1) - \rho_1 T_\theta(x, \tau, -\rho_1) &= \frac{y_1(x, \rho)}{2\omega_1} \left[\frac{F_2(\rho_1)}{F_1(\rho_1)} y_1(\tau, \rho) - y_2(\tau, \rho) \right] + \\ &+ \frac{1}{2\omega_1} \int_0^{\infty} \Gamma(x, t, \rho_1) \left[\frac{F_2(\rho_1)}{F_1(\rho_1)} y_1(\tau, \rho_1) - y_2(\tau, \rho_1) \right] y_1(t, \rho_1) dt + \\ &+ \frac{y_1(x, -\rho_1)}{2\omega_1} \left[\frac{F_2(-\rho_1)}{F_1(-\rho_1)} y_1(\tau, -\rho_1) - y_2(\tau, -\rho_1) \right] + \\ &+ \frac{1}{2\omega_1} \int_0^{\infty} \Gamma(x, t, -\rho_1) \left[\frac{F_2(-\rho_1)}{F_1(-\rho_1)} y_1(\tau, -\rho_1) - y_2(\tau, -\rho_1) \right] y_1(t, -\rho_1) dt = \\ &= \frac{1}{2\omega_1} \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{F_2((-1)^{3-i} \rho_1)}{F_1((-1)^{3-i} \rho_1)} \left[e^{\rho_1 \omega_i (x+\tau)} + \int_0^{\infty} \Gamma(x, t, (-1)^{3-i} \rho_1) e^{\rho_1 \omega_i (t+\tau)} dt \right] - \end{aligned}$$

$$-\frac{1}{2\omega_1} \sum_{i=1}^2 \left[e^{\rho_1 \omega_i (x-\tau)} + \int_0^\infty \Gamma(x,t, (-1)^{3-i} \rho_1) e^{\rho_1 (t-\tau)} dt \right].$$

And also for $\tau > x$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_1 T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho_1) - \rho_1 T_\theta(x, \tau, -\rho_1) &= \frac{1}{2\omega_1} \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{F_2((-1)^{3-i} \rho_1)}{F_1((-1)^{3-i} \rho_1)} \left[e^{\rho_1 \omega_i (x+\tau)} + \right. \\ &+ \left. \int_0^\infty \Gamma(x,t, (-1)^{3-i} \rho_1) e^{\rho_1 \omega_i (t+\tau)} dt \right] - \frac{1}{2\omega_i} \sum_{i=1}^2 \left[e^{\rho_1 \omega_i (\tau-x)} + \int_0^\infty \Gamma(x,t, (-1)^{3-i} \rho_1) e^{\rho_1 \omega_i (\tau-t)} dt \right]. \end{aligned}$$

So, we obtained that both for $\tau > x$ and for $\tau < x$

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_1 T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho_1) - \rho_1 T_\theta(x, \tau, -\rho_1) &= \frac{1}{2\omega_1} \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{F_2((-1)^{3-i} \rho_1)}{F_1((-1)^{3-i} \rho_1)} \left[e^{\rho_1 \omega_i (x+\tau)} + \right. \\ &+ \left. \int_0^\infty \Gamma(x,t, (-1)^{3-i} \rho_1) e^{\rho_1 \omega_i (t+\tau)} dt \right] - \frac{1}{2\omega_i} \sum_{i=1}^2 \left[e^{\rho_1 \omega_i |x-\tau|} + \int_0^\infty \Gamma(x,t, (-1)^{3-i} \rho_1) e^{\rho_1 \omega_i |t-\tau|} dt \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Denote by

$$\psi_1 y_1(x, \tau, \rho_1) = \frac{F_2((-1)^{3-i} \rho_1)}{F_1((-1)^{3-i} \rho_1)} e^{\rho_1 \omega_i (x+\tau)} + \int_0^\infty \Gamma(x,t, (-1)^{3-i} \rho_1) e^{\rho_1 \omega_i (t+\tau)} dt,$$

and

$$\psi_2 y_2(x, \tau, \rho_1) = e^{\rho_1 \omega_i |x-\tau|} - \int_0^\infty \Gamma(x,t, (-1)^{3-i} \rho_1) e^{\rho_1 \omega_i |t-\tau|} dt.$$

Then we obtain

$$\rho_1 T_\theta(x, \tau, \rho_1) - \rho_1 T_\theta(x, \tau, -\rho_1) = \frac{1}{2\omega_1} \sum_{i=1}^2 \psi_i y_i(x, \tau, \rho_1) \tag{3.11}$$

Substituting (3.11) in (3.10), we obtain

$$T_\theta(x, \tau, \lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{y_i(x) \overline{y_i(\tau)}}{(\lambda - \lambda_i)(y_i, y_i)} - \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\sum_{i=1}^2 \psi_i y_i(x, \tau, \rho_1)}{\rho_1^2 - \lambda} \tag{3.12}$$

So, we proved the following theorem

Theorem 3.2. If conditions 1), 2), 3) are fulfilled and $T_\theta(x, \tau, \lambda)$ is the Green functions of the integro-differential operator L_θ , then for any point λ not belonging to the spectrum of the integro-differential operator then L_θ is of the form (3.12) where the integral from the right converges absolutely and uniformly with respect to x, τ in the interval $0 \leq x, \tau < \infty$.

Using the M.A.Naimark method [2], it is easy to write expansion for $T_\theta(x, \tau, \lambda)$ when the zeros of $F_1(\rho)$ are multiple and if $F_1(\rho)$ has zeros on the real axis $\rho_1 = 0$

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